

Research Article

Clothes Box: A Dual-Functional Cloth Folding Box

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Abstract: Rapid economic changes have changed the individual lifestyle in which people are opt for convenience and time-efficient products. The common struggle for individuals with busy lifestyles is to spend their time in doing household chores. Majority agreed that traditional methods of folding clothes are often time-consuming and inefficient especially to those teenagers as well as grown-ups that have difficulties in folding their cloths properly. Besides, the consumptions of plastic bags and box for business apparels owners also cause negative impacts towards the environment. Thus, we come out with a fresh idea of clothes-box, a dual-functional cloth folding box that serves as a portable bag for business owner which can be reused as clothes folding box by the consumer thus maintaining neat and organized clothing. Clothes-box ensures sustainable consumptions and production patterns, improve the retail presentation for clothing business owners, helps saving time, promote neat and tidy lifestyle and can be as a basic learning tool for toddlers and children. Through strategic marketing as well as thorough consideration on costs and expenses, we are optimistic about our noteworthy increase in revenues and business growth in the near future.

Keywords: clothes folding box, packaging box, sustainable product

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13888329

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1. INTRODUCTION

Sustainability has become very synonymous with this era. People are demanding for more sustainable products that are not only functional but also eco-friendly. This is due to consumers are more environmentally conscious thus prefer to choose eco-friendly products in their daily lives. Modern production nowadays has to make sustainability as a critical factor in consumer product design

and integrate sustainable practices in their operations (Product Development, 2024). The continuous usage of non-sustainable products has worsened the condition of planet earth. For example, according to Dr. Rulia Akhtar, a Research Fellow at Ungku Aziz Centre for Development Studies in Universiti Malaya, plastic waste gives critical impacts towards humanity health and ecological nowadays. With an escalating numbers of plastic trash contamination, Malaysia's waste disposal system is facing formidable challenges. Although the consumption of disposable plastic bags in supermarkets and stores has decreased in the recent years, many other shops and small grocery stores are still continued to give out disposable bags to their consumers thus neglecting the negative consequences towards the environment including land and marine pollution, habitat damage and so on (Bernama Thoughts, 2023).

According to a survey report by Malaysia Population Research Hub (2017), Malaysian families are still very much traditional in terms of gender roles in which men will be the breadwinners while women are expected to be the caregiver that dedicated all of their time in doing household chores, taking care of the children, eldercare duties, etc. However, economic and development changes in Malaysia have gradually shift this lifestyle. Today, women have significant roles in society. Most of them are stated to join politics, doing business, entering corporate worlds and joining various industries. This eventually contribute to the social change (Total Risk Administration, 2024). While both husband and wife have similar responsibilities, limited time will be spent in doing household chores as well as educating their children on the basic aspects of self-management including having their belongings neat and tidy.

Pursuing sustainable product development as well as improving the lifestyle of the society, crucial actions need to be taken by the product manufacturers. Considering the positive impacts towards the environment, this study proposes a solution that could benefits both the business owners as well as individual consumer. Clothes Box aims to enhance the productivity of the society and business owners thus improving the lifestyle of the society and economy of the nation.

2. METHOD

An observation and informal interviews have been conducted prior the idea generation. The target respondents were our colleagues, business owners, students as well as parents with small kids. The respondents were asked informal questions so that we can find out potential solutions to their problems. For example, the respondents were asked about what daily chores they found very time consuming and what are the changes that they want in doing their household chores. The feedback from the respondents were documented and recorded for our future references.

3. PROPOSED IDEA: CLOTHES BOX

3.1 Functions and Features of the Clothes Box

From the data gathered by our team members, majority of the respondents are demanding for something useful, time efficient and sustainable product – thus brings us with this idea of clothes box. Basically, Clothes box's main function is to serve as a packaging box for the apparel business owner out there. The outer decoration of the box will be determined by the business owner prior the transaction. They can freely choose the readily designs prepared by the production team or sending their own designs. Later, completely-designed packaging box will be produced and delivered to business owners according to the quantity they ordered.

The second function of this clothes box is can be used as clothes folding box. In which, the customer can reuse the packaging box that they got earlier from the apparel shop to help them in folding their clothes. This box is expected to help in shorten the time spent for folding the never-ending everyday clean clothes. It can be used by any family members especially the kids and teenagers who's

in the learning process on how to manage and tidy up their things notable their wardrobe. Besides that, individual consumer also can buy Clothes Box from our social media platforms such as TikTok, Facebook and Instagram.

Clothes box will be designed by using high-quality art card paper, providing strength and durability of the product. Besides, this material is expected to protect the shirt inside when be using as a packaging box, and can serve it purpose of folding variety of fabrics to be folded. The size of the box will be 30cm in length, 5cm in height and 30cm in width which is specifically designed to fit the dimensions of a folded shirt, ensuring the best fit for standard size shirts. The lightweighted and the integrated handle of the packaging box allows for easy carrying. This is due to a die-cut handle that is crafted onto the art card paper to create a sturdy opening and makes the box easy to be carried as a packaging box. The box is also designed to be easily foldable thus allowing convenience clothes-folding experiences.

Figure 3.1. Proposed design for Clothes Box

3.2 Value Proposition

The value propositions of our idea are firstly, Clothes Box is a green product that durable enough to be reused with different functions for so many times and made of recyclable materials that reduce the negative impacts towards the environment. The production of the Clothes Box also will consider all those procedures highlighted for sustainable production.

Secondly, the dual function of Clothes box can improve the brand image of the apparel businesses as well as helps the consumers with their clothes folding task. For example, the attractiveness of our idea will help the business owner to market their brands and attract more customers whose making aesthetic as their prime consideration.

Besides the sustainability considerations of the packaging box as well as the attractive designs and dual functional of the Clothes Box that enhanced the overall shopping experience, Clothes Box can also help the consumers especially the busy parents and housewives in folding their clean clothes efficiently. By using Clothes Box to fold the clothes, they can have joyful moments with their kids in folding and tidying their folded clothes in the wardrobes.

3.3 Commercialization Potential

The main target customers for this product are apparel business owners, busy working people and housewives; as well as teenagers in boarding school. After considering the costs of materials and other associated costs, the price for individual consumer is set at RM6.50 per box while special discounts

up to 50% will be offered to business owners subjected to the quantity and design ordered. Online channel such as TikTok, Instagram and Facebook will be utilized in promoting Clothes Box. We will also encourage business owners to do contract packaging with us.

The production of Clothes Box will be conducted in Kota Bharu Kelantan. Given the lower cost of living and price of materials, Kelantan provides a competitive advantage to our business. Besides that, easy access, proximity to suppliers and potential customers also being as a critical consideration in selecting the location for the business.

4. CONCLUSION

As the conclusion, Clothes Box will be the trendsetter for the packaging business in the future. With a thorough research and development activities, we believe that our product will continue to grow and improve, adapting to our customers' needs. As we uniquely positioned our product as the first business to offer a groundbreaking dual functional approach, we are one step ahead from our competitors. Thus, making us passionate about the future and dedicated to lead the markets for years to come.

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